

Calcium chloride catalyzed one-pot three component synthesis of tetrasubstituted piperdines under solvent free using ultrasound condition and grinding condition

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Abstract : Calcium chloride was found an efficient catalyst for synthesis of tetrasubstituted piperdines through multi-component reaction between 2 equivalents of amines, 2 equivalents of benzaldehyde and 1 equivalent of ethyl acetoacetate under solvent free and ultrasound condition and grinding condition. This method has various advantages over other reported methods are inexpensive, easily available and safe to handle catalyst, short reaction time and high yield, and reaction is well tolerated with electron withdrawing as well as electron donating group, avoid use of toxic and heavy metals.

Keywords : Aldehyde, amine, calcium chloride, multicomponent reaction, piperdines, solvent free, ultrasound.

Introduction

Multicomponent Reactions (MCRs) are convergent reactions, in which three or more starting materials are taken in one vessel and react to form a single product, where basically all or most of the reactants are put in the newly formed product. In an MCR, a product is assembled according to a cascade of elementary chemical reactions. The challenge is to conduct an MCR in such a way that the network of pre-equilibrated reactions channel into the main product and do not yield side products. The result is clearly dependent on the reaction conditions : solvent, temperature, catalyst, concentration, the kind of starting materials and functional groups^{1,2}.

Many of the natural products contain nitrogen which is present in cyclic or acyclic form. The piperidine ring is present in most of the natural products like alkaloids and found in many drugs³. Thousands of piperidine nucleus are bare in clinical and preclinical studies⁴. The functionalized piperdines shows various biological activities like antihypertensive⁵, antibacterial⁶, anticonvulsant⁷, anti-inflammatory⁸ and antimalarial⁹. Furthermore, these are knottily involved in the monoamine oxidase (MAO)-based mechanism of Parkinson's disease¹⁰ and as inhibitors of farnesyl transferase¹¹ and dihydroorotate dehydrogenase¹². Substituted piperdines well-known as the note-

worthy class of therapeutic agents in the treatment of influenza infection¹³, anti-acetylcholinesterase activity¹⁴, viral infections including AIDS¹⁵, and diabetes¹⁶.

Due to this significant biological activity of highly substituted piperdines has attracted many researchers for their synthesis¹⁷ and a number of procedures have been developed for their synthesis. Reported methods for synthesis of piperdines are Tandem cyclopropane ring-opening/Conia-ene cyclization¹⁸, imino Diels-Alder reactions¹⁹, aza prins-cyclizations²⁰, intramolecular Michael reactions^{21,22}, intramolecular Mannich reactions on to iminium ions²³, cyclohydrocarboxylation²⁴, radical cyclization²⁵.

However, these methods have demerits like multistep synthesis and a poorer yield of the product, unsafe reaction condition. Now days the functionalized piperdines have been synthesized by using MCRs. Catalyst are used to synthesis of functionalized piperdines using MCRs are TBATB²⁶, oxalic acid dehydrate²⁷, LaCl₃.7H₂O in MeOH²⁸, acetic acid²⁹. Some other catalyst employing to carry this transformation are InCl₃³⁰, bromodimethylsulfonium bromide³¹, L-proline/TFA³², Cr(NO₃)₃.9H₂O³³, molecular I₂³⁴, CAN³⁵, ZrOCl₂.8H₂O³⁶, picric acid³⁷, thioureadioxide (TUD)³⁸, BF₃-SiO₂³⁹, VCl₃⁴⁰ and Bi(NO₃)₃.5H₂O⁴¹ as efficient catalysts. However, these methods suffer from disadvantage like use of expensive

Fig. 1. Various methods for synthesis of piperdines.

and surplus amount of catalysts, use of highly acidic catalyst, heavy and toxic metal which dissolved in water which affects on acquit life and longer reaction time and low yield. Therefore, there is a need for highly efficient, resourceful, and eco-friendly synthetic protocol to obtain these valuable compounds in good yields.

Present work :

Calcium chloride is inexpensive, harmless to the environment, and easily available. This salt has been used as an efficient Lewis base in an aldol reaction of dimethylsilyl enolates in aqueous *N,N*-dimethylformamide⁴², the Biginelli reaction⁴³, and in the formation of phosphonates⁴⁴, in three component Mannich reaction for synthesis of β -amino ketone⁴⁵, in synthesis of Mikaneic acid⁴⁶. In recent years ultrasound reaction attracted attention of most of the researchers due to reactions are fast, carried out solvent free and use of nonconventional heating. Using ultrasound condition organic transformation catalyzed are synthesis of ethyl α -cyanocinnamates⁴⁷, green synthesis of hexahydrotriazines⁴⁸, synthesis of anhydrides from acyl chlorides⁴⁹, synthesis of the Baylis-Hillman adducts⁵⁰, synthesis of *o*-hydroxyketone⁵¹.

To the best of our knowledge, one-pot synthesis of 1,2,4,6-tetrasubstituted piperdines catalyzed by calcium chloride have not been reported. Here, we report a calcium chloride catalyzed three components one-pot reaction of 2 equivalent of substituted benzaldehyde, 2 equivalent of aniline and 1 equivalent of β -keto ester that afford

tetrasubstituted piperdines under solvent free and ultrasound conditions.

Results and discussion

Our experiments established that stirring of 2 equivalent of substituted benzaldehyde, 2 equivalent of aniline and 1 equivalent of β -keto ester and 1 equivalent of calcium chloride in ethanol at room temperature for 24 h led to the formation of tetrasubstituted piperdines. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC and the structure of the product was confirmed by spectroscopic data. Next we decided to reduce the reaction time, for that we change the reaction condition from room temperature to heating at 60 °C and we observed that reaction time reduced to 2 h and achieved higher yields of pure product. Next we decided to carried same reaction under ultrasound and solvent free condition, we observed that starting material is consumed and formation of new products confirmed by TLC. The structure of product is confirmed by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and IR spectroscopy. Then, scope of the reaction was then studied by varying substituted benzaldehyde at *o*-, *m*-, *p*-position. The results are summarized in Table 1. Substrates bearing various functional groups such as CH₃, OCH₃, Cl, NO₂ and OH all reacted to produce the corresponding tetrasubstituted piperdines in moderate to good yield. *p*- and *m*-Substituted benzaldehydes gives good yield while *o*-substituted benzaldehydes gives low yield due to steric hindrance. When electron donating group present at *p*- and *m*-position yield of product is good and electron withdrawing group gave low yield.

Next, we decided to carry out the reaction under grinding condition. In mortar and pestle we take 2 equivalent benzaldehyde, 2 equivalent of amine, 1 equivalent of ethyl acetoacetate and 1 equivalent calcium chloride was taken as model reaction, and grind this reaction mixture. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC and the structure of the product was confirmed by spectroscopic data. The spectroscopic data match with authentic sample. Then, scope of the reaction was then studied by varying substituted benzaldehyde at *o*-, *m*-, *p*-position. Substrates bearing various functional groups such as CH₃, OCH₃, Cl, NO₂ and OH all reacted to produce the corresponding tetrasubstituted piperdines in moderate to good yield. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Kulkarni : Calcium chloride catalyzed one-pot three component synthesis of tetrasubstituted *etc.*

Scheme 1. One-pot three component synthesis of tetrasubstituted piperidines.

Table 1. Synthesis of functionalized piperidines using calcium chloride under ultrasound and grinding condition^a

Entry	Benzaldehyde (R ₁) (1)	Product (4)	Time in hours		Yield ^b		Melting point (°C)
			Ultrasound	Grinding	Ultrasound	Grinding	
1	H	4a	1.55	1.35	87	85	179–181
2	4-Me	4b	1.45	1.30	91	87	229–231
3	4-Cl	4c	2.25	2.10	84	81	163–166
4	4-NO ₂	4d	2.45	2.30	78	74	196–198
5	3-NO ₂	4e	2.25	2.20	83	78	185–187
6	2-NO ₂	4f	3.45	3.35	57	53	123–125
7	4-OMe	4g	1.50	1.45	89	85	167–169
8	4-Br	4h	2.10	2.00	85	81	232–235
9	4-OH	4i	2.15	2.10	82	76	203–204
10	4-NMe ₂	4j	2.15	2.10	79	73	155–158
11	4-F	4k	2.00	1.40	86	81	229–232
12	2-F	4l	3.20	3.15	45	34	129–131
13	2-Cl	4m	2.45	2.40	67	62	121–123
14	3-Br	4n	2.30	2.35	30	28	157–160
15	2-OMe	4o	3.15	3.15	46	38	123–125

^aAll compounds were characterized by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, IR. ^bIsolated yield.

Spectral analysis of synthesized functionalized piperidines :

(1) Ethyl 2,6-diphenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate :

m.p. 179–181 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3234, 1654, 1586, 1252 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.33 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz), 2.68 (1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz), 2.84 (1H, dd, *J* 5.3, 15 Hz), 4.24–4.32 (1H, m), 4.45–4.52 (1H, m), 5.12 (1H, s), 6.23–6.26 (2H, m), 6.41 (1H, s), 6.53 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz), 6.63 (1H, d, *J* 7.1 Hz), 7.02–7.08 (5H, m), 7.11–7.16 (2H, m),

7.18–7.24 (6H, m), 7.34 (1H, d, *J* 7.1 Hz), 10.24 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 15.1, 32.8, 55.5, 58.4, 59.1, 97.76, 112.2, 115.8, 125.4, 126.1, 126.1, 127.2, 128.34, 128.3, 128.8, 129.3, 137.4, 141.8, 144.5, 146.7, 155.9, 168.4.

(2) Ethyl 1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-2,6-dip-tolyl-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate : m.p. 229–231 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3229, 1658, 1583, 1247 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.29 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz), 2.32 (3H, s), 2.34 (3H, s), 2.71 (1H, dd, *J* 2.0, 15.0 Hz),

2.86 (1H, dd, *J* 15.0 Hz), 4.28–4.34 (1H, m), 4.48–4.53 (1H, m), 5.11 (1H, s), 6.27 (2H, d, *J* 7 Hz), 6.38 (1H, s), 6.49 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz), 6.57 (1H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz), 7.04–7.10 (11H, m), 7.17 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz), 10.21 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 15.7, 21.2, 21.3, 33.1, 55.8, 58.5, 59.8, 98.4, 112.4, 116.1, 125.5, 125.7, 126.2, 126.9, 128.7, 129.4, 137.8, 141.2, 144.4, 146.9, 156.4, 168.8.

(3) Ethyl 2,6-bis(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate : m.p. 163–166 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3236, 1663, 1589, 1251 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.42 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz), 2.76 (1H, d, *J* 15.0 Hz), 2.87 (1H, dd, *J* 5.2, 15.0 Hz), 4.32–4.36 (1H, m), 4.52–4.56 (1H, m), 5.14 (1H, s), 6.36 (1H, s), 6.42 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 6.52 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 6.73 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.06 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.09 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.14 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.19 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 7.28–7.42 (5H, m), 10.32 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 16.2, 34.4, 54.9, 58.4, 59.5, 98.8, 113.2, 116.5, 125.9, 126.7, 127.4, 128.6, 128.9, 129.2, 129.5, 132.6, 133.3, 137.5, 141.3, 142.7, 147.7, 156.8, 168.7.

(4) Ethyl 2,6-bis(4-nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate : m.p. 196–198 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3234, 1662, 1592, 1249 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.52 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz), 4.54–4.57 (1H, m), 4.64–4.68 (1H, m), 5.39 (1H, s), 6.42–6.45 (2H, m), 6.47–6.50 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 6.54 (1H, s), 6.73–6.75 (1H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz), 7.13–7.18 (5H, m), 7.48–7.53 (3H, m), 7.64–7.67 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.94 (1H, s), 8.13–8.16 (2H, m), 8.34 (1H, s), 10.35 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 15.3, 33.9, 55.3, 58.0, 60.4, 67.8, 97.4, 113.5, 117.8, 121.67, 121.8, 122.3, 123.8, 125.4, 126.4, 129.7, 130.2, 134.9, 137.7, 144.5, 148.3, 155.5, 168.4.

(5) Ethyl 2,6-bis(3-nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate : m.p. 185–187 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3232, 1661, 1587, 1251 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.56–1.58 (3H, t, *J* 6.0 Hz), 2.89–2.91 (2H, s), 4.38–4.42 (1H, m), 4.54–4.58 (1H, m), 5.32 (1H, s), 6.40–6.43 (2H, m), 6.47–6.50 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 6.52 (1H, s), 6.72–6.74 (1H, t, *J* 6.0 Hz), 7.12–7.18 (5H, m), 7.43–7.52 (3H, m), 7.64–7.69 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.96 (1H, s), 8.14–8.19 (2H, m), 8.32 (1H, s), 10.35 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 14.8, 25.6, 33.8, 55.2, 57.0, 60.3, 67.9, 97.0, 113.1, 117.7, 121.4, 121.7, 121.8, 122.5, 125.6, 126.5, 129.1, 129.3, 129.4, 129.7, 132.3, 132.6, 137.2, 144.5, 145.8, 146.4, 148.6, 148.7, 155.3, 167.7.

(6) Ethyl 2,6-bis(2-nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate : m.p. 123–125 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3237, 1664, 1592, 1246 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.58–1.61 (3H, t, *J* 6.0 Hz), 2.91–2.94 (2H, s), 4.42–4.45 (1H, m), 4.58–4.62 (1H, m), 5.37 (1H, s), 6.42–6.44 (2H, m), 6.51–6.53 (2H, m), 6.57 (1H, s), 6.75–6.77 (1H, m), 7.14–7.17 (5H, m), 7.46–7.51 (3H, m), 7.66–7.68 (1H, m), 7.93 (1H, s), 8.08–8.11 (2H, m), 8.28 (1H, s), 10.31 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 15.2, 26.3, 34.5, 56.5, 58.2, 61.2, 68.3, 97.6, 114.3, 118.2, 122.2, 123.4, 124.2, 124.8, 126.2, 127.2, 129.7, 130.2, 131.2, 131.8, 133.4, 134.2, 138.1, 145.2, 146.2, 146.7, 148.9, 149.4, 156.4, 168.9.

(7) Ethyl 2,6-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate : m.p. 167–169 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3231, 1653, 1578, 1252 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.19 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz),

2.68 (1H, dd, *J* 2.0, 15.0 Hz), 2.82 (1H, dd, *J* 15.0 Hz), 3.85 (3H, s), 4.26–4.31 (1H, m), 4.42–4.47 (1H, m), 5.13 (1H, s), 6.24 (2H, d, *J* 7 Hz), 6.35 (1H, s), 6.46 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz), 6.52 (1H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz), 7.02–7.08 (11H, m), 7.14 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz), 10.25 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 15.1, 21.3, 33.5, 55.5, 56.4, 58.1, 59.6, 98.2, 113.3, 116.4, 125.8, 126.2, 126.8, 127.1, 128.4, 128.7, 129.3, 129.6, 136.2, 141.5, 145.0, 146.7, 156.4, 169.8.

(8) Ethyl 2,6-bis(4-bromophenyl)-1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate : m.p. 232–235 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3231, 1664, 1586, 1246 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.37 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz), 2.67 (1H, d, *J* 15.0 Hz), 2.83 (1H, dd, *J* 5.2, 15.0 Hz), 4.28–4.33 (1H, m), 4.43–4.47 (1H, m), 5.12 (1H, s), 6.32 (1H, s), 6.44 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz) 6.54 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 6.68 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.04 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.05 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz) 7.12 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.18 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 7.24–7.38 (5H, m), 10.29 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 16.4, 34.1, 54.6, 58.1, 58.2, 98.6, 113.6, 116.2, 125.4, 126.1, 127.5, 128.3, 128.7, 129.1, 129.7, 132.3, 133.2, 137.4, 141.1, 142.3, 147.9, 156.4, 168.2.

(9) Ethyl 2,6-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate : m.p. 203–204 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3342, 3228, 1656, 1583, 1254 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.23 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz), 2.62 (1H, dd, *J* 2.0, 15.0 Hz), 2.79 (1H, dd, *J* 15.0 Hz), 4.32–4.34 (1H, m), 4.48–4.52 (1H, m), 5.10 (1H, s), 6.21 (2H, d, *J* 7 Hz), 6.32 (1H, s), 6.46 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz), 6.48 (1H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz), 7.04–7.09 (11H, m), 7.16 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz), 10.27 (1H, s), 11.23 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 15.3, 21.7, 33.8, 54.9, 56.7, 58.5, 59.2, 97.8, 112.8, 116.8, 125.4, 126.5, 126.9, 127.8, 129.2, 129.8, 130.3, 131.2, 135.3, 140.2, 144.4, 146.2, 155.8, 168.3.

(10) Ethyl 2,6-bis(4-(dimethylamino)phenyl)-1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate : m.p. 155–158 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3224, 1651, 1574, 1254 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.14 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz), 2.57 (1H, dd, *J* 2.0, 15.0 Hz), 2.71 (1H, dd, *J* 15.0 Hz), 3.02–3.05 (6H, s), 4.23–4.28 (1H, m), 4.32–4.36 (1H, m), 5.05 (1H, s), 6.16 (2H, d, *J* 7 Hz), 6.27 (1H, s), 6.38 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz), 6.45 (1H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz), 7.02–7.07 (11H, m), 7.13 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz), 10.18 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 14.6, 21.3, 33.4, 41.3, 54.4, 56.3, 58.2, 59.5, 97.2, 112.2, 115.2, 124.1, 125.2, 126.3, 127.4, 128.4, 129.4, 130.1, 131.1, 135.9, 141.3, 149.4, 149.8, 167.9.

(11) Ethyl 2,6-bis(4-fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate : m.p. 229–232 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3244, 3021, 1661, 1543, 1245 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.42–1.45 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz), 2.73–2.75 (1H, d, *J* 20 Hz), 2.85–2.89 (1H, dd, *J* 15.0 Hz), 4.32–4.34 (1H, m), 4.44–4.47 (1H, m), 5.16 (1H, s), 6.35 (1H, s), 6.41–6.44 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz), 6.52–6.55 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz), 6.63–6.67 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 7.05–7.08 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz), 7.13–7.23 (7H, m), 7.43–7.46 (4H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 10.34 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 14.6, 33.2, 54.5, 57.1, 59.6, 97.4, 112.4, 116.2, 120.5, 120.9, 125.3, 125.8, 127.9, 128.6, 128.9, 129.5, 131.3, 132.1, 137.3, 141.2, 142.9, 146.8, 155.3, 167.7.

(12) Ethyl 2,6-bis(2-fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate : m.p. 129–131 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3234, 3043, 1648, 1588, 1247 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.42–1.44 (3H, t, *J* 6.0 Hz), 2.94–2.97 (2H, m), 4.25–4.31 (2H, m), 4.36–4.41 (1H, m), 5.41 (1H, s), 6.37–6.41 (2H, s), 6.54–6.58 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 6.61 (1H, s), 6.71–6.76 (1H, t, *J* 6.0 Hz), 7.03–7.21 (13H, m).

(13) Ethyl 2,6-bis(4-(dimethylamino)phenyl)-1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate : m.p. 155–158 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3224, 1651, 1574, 1254 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.14 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz), 2.57 (1H, dd, *J* 2.0, 15.0 Hz), 2.71 (1H, dd, *J* 15.0 Hz), 3.02–3.05 (6H, s), 4.23–4.28 (1H, m), 4.32–4.36 (1H, m), 5.05 (1H, s), 6.16 (2H, d, *J* 7 Hz), 6.27 (1H, s), 6.38 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz), 6.45 (1H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz), 7.02–7.07 (11H, m), 7.13 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz), 10.18 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 14.6, 21.3, 33.4, 41.3, 54.4, 56.3, 58.2, 59.5, 97.2, 112.2, 115.2, 124.1, 125.2, 126.3, 127.4, 128.4, 129.4, 130.1, 131.1, 135.9, 141.3, 149.4, 149.8, 167.9.

m), 10.23 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 13.9, 31.3, 52.4, 52.6, 59.6, 97.2, 113.4, 115.2, 115.7, 116.7, 117.2, 117.7, 123.9, 124.1, 124.6, 125.1, 125.9, 126.3, 128.4, 128.7, 129.2, 129.6, 129.8, 130.0, 130.1, 130.3, 130.8, 130.9, 138.3, 146.6, 155.8, 158.3, 159.7, 161.6, 162.4, 168.5.

(13) Ethyl 2,6-bis(2-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate :

m.p. 121–123 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3232, 3038, 1645, 1582, 1243, cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 1.41–1.43 (3H, t, J 6.0 Hz), 2.91–2.95 (2H, m), 4.23–4.28 (2H, m), 4.33–4.37 (1H, m), 5.32 (1H, s), 6.39–6.44 (2H, s), 6.57–6.61 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 6.64 (1H, s), 6.74–6.78 (1H, t, J 6.0 Hz), 7.02–7.18 (13H, m), 10.21 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 13.7, 31.4, 52.7, 52.9, 59.2, 97.1, 113.6, 114.9, 115.2, 116.5, 117.1, 117.9, 124.0, 124.3, 124.8, 125.3, 126.0, 126.6, 128.2, 128.9, 129.1, 129.7, 129.9, 130.2, 130.4, 130.5, 130.8, 131.2, 137.9, 145.8, 155.2, 158.1, 159.3, 161.4, 162.1, 168.2.

(14) Ethyl 2,6-bis(3-bromophenyl)-1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate :

m.p. 157–160 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3253, 3063, 1642, 1584, 1248 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 1.42–1.46 (3H, t, J 8.0 Hz), 2.72–2.75 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 2.85–2.87 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 4.31–4.38 (1H, m), 4.47–4.52 (1H, m), 5.12 (1H, s), 6.32–6.36 (3H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 6.44–6.47 (2H, d, J 12.0 Hz), 6.63–6.66 (1H, t, J 8.0 Hz), 7.06–7.22 (9H, m), 7.23 (1H, s), 7.35–7.38 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 7.42–7.45 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 7.57 (1H, s), 10.31 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 14.4, 33.2, 54.5, 57.6, 59.2, 97.6, 113.4, 117.2, 122.4, 125.4, 125.8, 126.3, 126.6, 129.2, 129.2, 129.9, 130.2, 130.5, 130.8, 131.2, 137.3, 145.5, 146.8, 147.3, 155.4, 167.2.

(15) Ethyl 2,6-bis(2-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate :

m.p. 123–125 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3242, 3039, 1645, 1587, 1253 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 1.32–1.36 (3H, t, J 8.0 Hz), 2.68–2.73 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 2.82–2.84 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 3.84 (3H, s), 4.26–4.28 (1H, m), 4.41–4.46 (1H, m), 5.08 (1H, s), 6.31–6.34 (3H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 6.41–6.43 (2H, d, J 12.0 Hz), 6.59–6.62 (1H, t, J 8.0 Hz), 7.03–7.19 (9H, m), 7.25 (1H, s), 7.32–7.35 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 7.41–7.46 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 7.53 (1H, s), 10.21 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 13.7, 32.9, 54.3, 56.3, 57.2, 59.1, 97.2, 112.7, 117.1, 121.6, 124.2, 125.2, 126.1, 126.7, 128.1, 128.7, 129.3, 129.9, 130.2, 130.4, 131.1, 137.5, 144.7, 145.3, 146.9, 155.4, 167.8.

Conclusion

In conclusion, here we reported a novel and simple method for the synthesis of highly functionalized piperidines using calcium chloride as a catalyst via one-pot five component reactions from easily available starting materials. Some advantages of this method are easily available and inexpensive catalyst, reaction condition is simple to carry out reaction, absence of tedious separation and purification procedures.

Experimental

Melting points determined by using open capillary method and are uncorrected. Infrared (IR) spectra of all compounds were measured a Shimadzu IR-460 spectrometer, respectively. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-400 Avance instrument with CDCl_3 as a solvent and TMS as an internal standard.

General procedure for the synthesis of piperidines under ultrasound condition :

Mixture of aromatic aldehyde (2 mmol), aniline (2 mmol) and β -keto ester (1 mmol) and calcium chloride (1 mmol) was irradiated under sonochemical condition at 33 KHz for the required period of time and progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of reaction, solid was obtained, which was treated with water followed by ethanol (2×10) and recrystallized from ethanol to afford pure piperidines.

General procedure for the synthesis of piperidines under grinding condition :

A mixture of aromatic aldehyde (2 mmol), aniline (2 mmol) and β -keto ester (1 mmol), calcium chloride (1 mmol) was grounded in a mortar with a pestle for the required period of time. On completion of the reaction as monitored by TLC, the obtained solid was treated with 10 ml water, followed by ethanol (2 \times 10) to get desired product. Further purification was achieved by recrystallized from ethanol to afford pure piperidines.

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